

Leverage of Pyridine Isomer on Phenothiazine Core: Organic Semiconductors as Selective layer in Perovskite Solar Cells

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Abstract

To drive the development of perovskite solar cells (PSCs), hole transporting materials are imperative. In this context pyridine derivatives are being probed as small molecules based hole-transporting materials due to their Lewis base and electron-deficient unit. Herein, we focused our investigation on pyridine isomer molecules: 4,4'-(10-(pyridin-*x*-yl)-10*H*-phenothiazine-3,7-diyl)bis(*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline) (*x* = **2**, **3**, or **4**), in which the pyridine nitrogen heteroatom is located at the 2, 3, and 4 positions, named as **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn**, respectively. We decipher the structure–properties–device performance relationship impacted by different *N*-atom positions in pyridine. In the case of **3PyPTPDAn**, the partial orbital overlap between HOMO and LUMO favors the generation of neutral excitons and

hole transport, as well as the improve form-formation ability and this induces efficient hole extraction as compared to their 2,4 analogs. The fabricated solar cells with **3PyPTPDAn** gave on par photovoltaic performance as of typical Spiro-OMeTAD, and higher than that of **2PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn**. The hydrophobicity and homogenous film properties of **3PyPTPDAn** add merits to the stability. This work emphasizes the guidelines to develop small molecules for organic solar cells, organic light-emitting diode, and thermally activated delayed fluorescence.

Keywords: Organic semiconductors; Pyridine Isomer; Phenothiazine; perovskite solar cells; Electron paramagnetic resonance

1. Introduction

The rapid evolution of organic-inorganic perovskite solar cells (PSCs) has attracted enormous attention within the last decade, which stemmed from their effective photovoltaic (*PV*) performance with >25% power conversion efficiency (PCE), simple and cost-effective solution-processability, and the potential for large-scale commercialization.¹⁻⁴ The best performance of PSC is displayed by the *n-i-p* device structure, where the perovskite as light harvester is layered between top hole/bottom electron selective layers, respectively.^{5,6} The hole-selective layers (HSLs) are substantial to expedite photo-generated hole extraction, transport and hinder the degradation of the perovskite layers.^{7,8}

Currently, 2,2',7,7'-tetrakis-(*N,N*-di-*p*-methoxyphenylamine)-9,9'-Spirobifluorene (Spiro-OMeTAD), enjoys to be the most studied HSL for PSCs and also delivered efficient performance contributing to the state-of-the-art.^{7,9} However, the drawbacks including demanding synthetic process, expensive cost of Spiro-bifluorene central core, and poor transportability in its pristine

state, hampers the upscaling of the perovskite-based solar cells and modules.¹⁰⁻¹² Organic small molecules are considered to be attractive alternatives for Spiro-OMeTAD, are being designed and synthesized, owing to important merits such as low batch-to-batch variations, tuneable properties *via* molecular engineering, cost-efficient, and simplified purification process.¹³⁻¹⁵

In this context, organic small molecules consisting of pyridine (Py) unit either in the core or arms have been investigated as HSLs. Pyridine unit by virtue of being Lewis base can also passivate the lead ion (Pb²⁺) defects at the surface and grain boundaries.¹⁶⁻²⁵ More importantly, it was considered as an electron-deficient unit to construct D-A-type HSLs. Up to now, the research on pyridine derivative unit in HSLs (**Figure 1**) could be categorized into two groups: (i) comparison of pyridine-based HSLs and counterparts with benzene unit, for instance, YZ22 (Py) *vs.* YZ18 (Ben),¹⁹ H-Pyr (Py) *vs.* H-Ben (Ben),¹⁶ and PT-DC (Py) *vs.* BP-DC (Ben)¹⁸; (ii) linking topology of core and arm such as 2,6PyDAnCBZ with 2,6-substitution *vs.* 3,5PyDAnCBZ with 3,5-substitution.²¹ Similar topology linking research in pyridine unit-based polymer has been reported.¹⁷ Such investigation guided us to develop small molecules based on innovative pyridine derivatives with linking topology as effective HSLs.

However, the impact of pyridine isomer in such small molecules-based HSLs has not been investigated yet. To develop effective materials and quantify the *N*-atom position influence on material's properties, and its translation into device performance, we designed and synthesized three new pyridine-based positional isomers: 4,4'-(10-(pyridin-*X*-yl)-10*H*-phenothiazine-3,7-diyl)bis(*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline) (*x*=**2**, **3**, or **4**), named as **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn**, respectively. Here the core was composed of the pyridine unit connected with phenothiazine at its *N*-position and the common end arms: 4-(*N,N*-di-4-anisyl-amino)benzo as core ended up at 3-, and 8-position of phenothiazine. Phenothiazine is an electron-rich heterocyclic

compound and resembles butterfly confirmation, which is effective in avoiding molecular aggregation.^{26–28} We optimized the structure-property relationships, by tuning the *N*-atom position of pyridine, and proved the electronic properties, film-formation ability, and fabricated PSCs.

Figure 1 The molecular structure of various pyridine-based HSL reported: XJ2,²⁹ XJ3,²⁹ F22,²⁵ F33,²⁵ JY8,³⁰ PT-DC,²² MD-T,³¹ MD-C,³¹ PTZ-1,²³ PTZ-2,²³ SPS-SPX-2TPA,³² D105,²⁰ D106 (H-Pyr),^{16,20} 3,6-Pyr,²⁴ 2,7-Pyr,²⁴ PTZ-Py,¹⁸ CZ-Py,³³ M6,³⁴ 2,6PyDAnCBZ,²¹ and

3,5PyDAnCBZ,²¹ and the isomer effects of pyridine based HSLs: **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn**.

2. Results and discussion

2.1 Synthesis

The pyridine-based isomers: **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** were synthesized using Buchwald-Hartwig coupling reaction and the detailed synthetic procedure is given in Scheme S1 (Supporting information). The step-by-step synthesis of phenothiazine precursor, 4,4'-(10H-phenothiazine-3,7-diyl)bis(*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline) (**PTPDAn**) is presented in the Supporting Information. Intermediate **PTPDAn** was synthesized in multiple steps, including Buchwald-Hartwig and Suzuki cross-coupling reactions. The Buchwald-Hartwig reaction of **PTPDAn** with 2-bromopyridine in the presence of Pd(OAc)₂ catalyst and NaO^tBu as a base in toluene at 110 °C for 20 h resulted in 4,4'-(10-(pyridine-2-yl)-10H-phenothiazine-3,7-diyl)bis(*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline) (**2PyPTPDAn**) in 62% yield. Similarly, 4,4'-(10-(pyridin-3-yl)-10H-phenothiazine-3,7-Diyl)bis(*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline) (**3PyPTPDAn**) and 4,4'-(10-(pyridin-4-yl)-10H-Phenothiazine-3,7-diyl)bis(*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline) (**4PyPTPDAn**) were synthesized using the similar procedure by the reaction of **PTPDAn** with 3-bromopyridine and 4-bromopyridine in 56% and 50% yield, respectively. It is worth mentioning that the yield of pyridine isomers HSLs is higher than that of commercial Spiro-OMeTAD (45% reported by Seok *et al.*).³⁵ The molecular structure of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** was established by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR spectroscopy, and HRMS (Figure S1–S11). Figure S12 displays the visual image of the dissolved materials in an organic solvent at room temperature for 5 minutes. Traces of undissolved particles

can be noted in the case of the **2PyPTPDAn**, while **3PyPTPDAn** and **4PyPTPDAn** are very well dispersed. Further, the solubility of pyridine-based HSL with dopants (lithium salt and *t*-BP) has a similar effect, indicating that the solubility of designed HSLs was controlled by the *N*-atom position in pyridine.

2.2 Photophysical and electrochemical properties

The UV-vis absorption spectra of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** were recorded in an organic solvent, (**Figure 2a**) and the data are summarized (**Table 1**). The absorption peaks of the Py-based HSLs are at 305 and 349 nm for **2PyPTPDAn**, at 309 and 334 nm for **3PyPTPDAn**, while at 310 and 348 nm for **4PyPTPDAn**, this corresponds to the π - π^* electronic transition and the intramolecular charge transfer from the donor to the acceptor moieties in the conjugated molecular system, respectively. The relative broad absorption peak of **3PyPTPDAn** than of **2PyPTPDAn** and **4PyPTPDAn** suggests the improved charge transfer in the molecules. The optical bandgap for **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** are 3.09, 2.85, and 2.92 eV, respectively, derived by following the equation: $E_g^{\text{opt}} = 1240/\lambda_{\text{onset}}$.

The redox behavior of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** was evaluated by cyclic voltammetry (CV) analysis (**Figure 2b**). It showed two oxidation peaks associated with donor methoxy substituted triphenylamine and phenothiazine moiety.²⁷ The highest occupied molecular orbital (E_{HOMO}) values were at -5.64 eV, -5.60 eV and -5.71 eV for **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn**, respectively, using the equation: $E_{\text{HOMO}} = -5.11 - (E_{\text{ox}}^{1/2} \text{ vs Fc/Fc}^+)$, where ($E_{\text{ox}}^{1/2} \text{ vs Fc/Fc}^+$) is the first half-wave oxidation value of the first oxidation waves.^{21,36,37} The lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (E_{LOMO}) for **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** at -2.55 eV, -2.75 eV, and -2.79 eV, respectively, obtained by the following

equation: $E_{LUMO} = E_{HOMO} - E_g^{opt}$. The energy level diagram of Py-based HSLs along with perovskite and gold electrode demonstrate that the HSL are energetically benign for the hole extraction and transport (the conduction and valence band value of perovskite is from the literature³⁸).

Figure 2 (a) Normalized UV-Vis absorption spectra of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** in dichloromethane, (b) cyclic voltammograms of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn**, (c) thermogravimetric analysis curves of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** at a heating rate of $5^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ under a nitrogen atmosphere, (d) differential scanning calorimetry curves of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** at a rate of $10^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$, (e) I - V curves for conductivity measurement for devices with ITO/HSL/Ag structure, and (f) J - V curves for mobility measurement for the hole-only device with FTO/PEDOT:PSS/HSL/Au structure. Top-view SEM images for the perovskite with (g) **2PyPTPDAn**, (h) **3PyPTPDAn**, and (i) **4PyPTPDAn** films.

Table 1. Photophysical and electrochemical data of HSLs.

HSL	$\lambda_{max}/\lambda_{onset}$ (nm)	E_g^{opt}/E_g^b	E_{HOMO} (eV)	E_{LUMO} (eV)	T_d (°C)	T_g (°C)	Conductivity ^c ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	Mobility ^c ($10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
2PyPTPDAn	305/349	3.09/3.48	-5.64 ^a /-4.85 ^b	-2.55 ^a /-1.30 ^b	206	109	0.28	3.0
3PyPTPDAn	309/334	2.85/3.13	-5.60 ^a /-4.80 ^b	-2.75 ^a /-1.67 ^b	223	120	0.46	5.4
4PyPTPDAn	310/348	2.79/3.35	-5.71 ^a /-4.89 ^b	-2.79 ^a /-1.40 ^b	265	128	0.02	0.3

^a) E_{HOMO} , E_{LUMO} , and bandgap estimated from the redox potential in cyclic voltammetry and UV-vis absorption spectra; ^b) DFT calculations of HSLs: $E_{LUMO}=E_{HOMO} + E_g$, ^c) HSL without dopants.

The thermal properties for **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** were investigated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) (Figure 2c&2d). The decomposition temperature (T_d) corresponding to 5% weight loss temperature for **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** are 206 °C, 223 °C, and 265 °C, respectively. We noted the second-heating run DSC curves of the HSLs, suggesting its amorphous nature, and the T_g value of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** appear at 109 °C, 120 °C, and 128 °C, respectively, similar to Spiro-OMeTAD (~ 127 °C). The T_d and T_g follows the order of **4PyPTPDAn** > **3PyPTPDAn** > **2PyPTPDAn**. It was pointed out that the symmetrical 4-position substitution gives improved thermal stability compared with the asymmetrical 2- and 3-position isomers.

The electrical measurements were performed to elucidate the influence of *N*-atom at pyridine in HSLs.^{13,21} The conductivities of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn** and, **4PyPTPDAn** were 0.28, 0.46, and 0.02 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, respectively and were in the range of pristine Spiro-OMeTAD (1.0 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$).²¹ The highest conductivity for **3PyPTPDAn** as compared to other isomers stem from the improved intramolecular charge transfer (shown by UV-vis absorption) and the density functional theory calculations (detailed in next section). The hole mobilities of pristine **2PyPTPDAn**,

3PyPTPDAn, and **4PyPTPDAn** were 3.0×10^{-4} , 5.4×10^{-4} , and 0.4×10^{-4} $\text{cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, respectively, derived by fitting the $J^{0.5}-V$ curves obtained from the hole-only devices following the Mott-Gurney square law ($J=9\epsilon\epsilon_0\mu V_{\text{app}}^2/8L^3$). We noted higher mobility for **3PyPTPDAn** than that for **2PyPTPDAn** and **4PyPTPDAn**, owing to the improved intermolecular π - π interaction as a result of the more planar structure, which is following their absorption spectra. However, **4PyPTPDAn** owned the lowest transportability that stem from the 4-position substitution.

The film-formation abilities and surface properties of HSLs on perovskite was examined by the scanning electron microscope (SEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) analysis before the fabrication of PSCs. The HSLs with dopants were spin-coated on the FTO/*b&mp*-TiO₂/perovskite substrates (Figure 2g–2i). The pyridine-based HSLs exhibited full coverage on the perovskite layers, and the perovskite/**3PyPTPDAn** depicted highly uniform and dense layers without pin-holes and aggregates, while perovskite with **2PyPTPDAn** and **4PyPTPDAn** images showed aggregates or undissolved dopants, respectively. A similar observation was noted from with topographical images (Figure S13), with a root mean square roughness values of 5.5, 4.0, and 4.5 nm for **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn**, respectively. The variation in solubility induced by the *N*-atom position in pyridine influence the microstructure. Besides, the pyridine unit is incorporated into HSLs with different *N*-atom positions, the possible interaction between HSLs and dopants can control the surface microstructure. The homogeneity provided by **3PyPTPDAn** will ensure effective interfacial contact between perovskite and hole selective layer and will allow performance enhancement.

The density functional theory (DFT) calculations at the B3LYP/6-31G(d) level was performed on **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** to explore their molecule architecture and the energy distribution at the ground state. **Figure 3** portrayed the theoretically

calculated E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} , respectively. In the case of *HOMO*, the electron cloud of 2, 4 Py-based HSLs are delocalized throughout the 4-(*N,N*-di-4-anisylamino)benzo arm and phenothiazine, while in the case of **3PyPTPDAn** it extends to the pyridine unit, and the larger distribution of electron cloud suggests improved conjugation and carrier transport.³⁹ In contrast, the *LUMO* of 2,4 Py-based HSLs is mainly located on the pyridine and extends to the phenothiazine of the donor **PTPDAn** unit. However, the *LUMO* of **3PyPTPDAn** is completely located on pyridine. While in the case of **3PyPTPDAn**, the partial orbital overlap between *LUMO* and *HOMO* favors the generation of neutral excitons and hole transport. Thus **3PyPTPDAn** exhibits improved hole transport performance compare to their 2,4 analogs.^{40,41} The theoretically determined E_{HOMO} of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** are -4.85 eV, -4.80 eV, and -4.89 eV, respectively, while the E_{LUMO} levels of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** are -1.30 eV, -1.67 eV, and -1.40 eV, respectively. The simulation results are consistent with the experimental *CV* data. The dihedral angles between the pyridine unit and the phenothiazine moiety for **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** evaluated from the ground state optimized structures are 89.85° , 87.79° , and 89.92° respectively. The **3PyPTPDAn** exhibits a relatively lower angle and owns a more planar configuration to improve the intermolecular π - π^* interaction which leads to comparatively high hole mobility than their 2,4 analogs.^{42,43}

Figure 3 Energy level diagram showing the E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} levels of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** were determined at the B3LYP/6-31G, (d) level, and the dihedral angles of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn**, respectively.

We run the electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) measurements for powder, pristine and doped states in organic solvent of HSLs. First, the X-band EPR spectra were recorded at room temperature on 25 mM toluene solution of the three pyridine isomer-based HSLs. Before the addition of dopant (lithium salt and *t*-BP), the solutions were almost EPR discreet, however after doping clear signals were detected. We accumulated fifty spectra to obtain substantial signals (**Figure 4**). The observation of three lines with intensity ratios close to 1:1:1 indicates the presence of an unpaired electron interacting mainly with a ^{14}N nucleus ($I=1$), ascribed to the spin (hole) formation in the phenothiazine entities after doping. Besides, the generation of other radicals with a very short lifetime ($<10^{-6}$ s) cannot be disregarded. The fitting of the spectra, using a computer simulation program functioning at the second order of the perturbation theory, gives g_{iso} values of 2.0061, 2.0064, and 2.0065 for the **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn**, respectively agrees with those observed in other *N*-substituted phenothiazine cation radicals.^{44,45} The hyperfine coupling constant (a^{N}) is significantly lower for **4PyPTPDAn** (5.2 Gauss) than for **2PyPTPDAn**

(6.2 Gauss) and **3PyPTPDAn** (6.3 Gauss). It is worthy to note that the intensity of the signal is an order of magnitude lower for **4PyPTPDAn**. On comparing doped HSLs and Spiro-OMeTAD (Figure S14c), the signal from Spiro-OMeTAD is stronger than pyridine-based HSLs, originated due to the high concentration of Spiro-OMeTAD (60 mM) used as compared to pyridine based HSLs (25 mM). Another plausible reason is very short-lived radicals that are difficult to detect easily for pyridine-based HSLs. In all the order, the hyperfine coupling constant indicated that the **3PyPTPDAn** owned the improved electron density compared to the other two isomers.

EPR spectra were also recorded on solid samples at room temperature operating at both, X- and Q-bands (Figure S14 and Table S1). The presence of holes is also confirmed in the solid-state, as well as the coupling between its $S=1/2$ electronic spin with the nuclear spin $I=1$ of a neighboring ^{14}N nucleus. The best resolution of the Q-band spectra allows us to determine the main components of the g and A tensors (Table S1), that exhibit near axial symmetry with $g_{\perp} > g_{\parallel} \approx 2.0023$ usually observed in planar organic radicals. The observation of the hyperfine structure in spectra implies that the exchange between the radicals is not strong in the solids probably due to their low concentration.

Figure 4. Room temperature EPR spectra registered on toluene at X-band for pristine and doped HSLs: (a) **2PyPTPDAn**, (b) **3PyPTPDAn**, and (c) **4PyPTPDAn**, respectively.

2.3 Device performance

To identify the impact of pyridine isomers small molecule-based HSLs on the PV performance, we fabricated PSC with $n-i-p$ structure and the cross-sectional SEM image (Figure 5b & Figure S15) of the PSC with **3PyPTPDAn** showed clear layered topologies, where the thickness of perovskite and **3PyPTPDAn** are ~ 440 nm and 105 nm, respectively. The $J-V$ curves of the PSCs with developed HSLs (Figure 5c) under standard AM 1.5 G irradiation (100 mW cm^{-2}) are displayed and the corresponding PV parameters are summarized (**Table 2**).

The **2PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs deliver a PCE of 16.05% with a V_{oc} of 1041.7 mV, a short-circuit current (J_{sc}) of 23.36 mA cm^{-2} , and a fill factor (FF) of 66.0%, while the **3PyPTPDAn**-based PSC yielded a relatively higher PCE of 17.93%, with a V_{oc} of 1047.0 mV, a short-circuit current (J_{sc}) of 23.79 mA cm^{-2} , and a FF of 72.0%. The higher FF stems from the improved electrical conductivity and hole mobility. In contrast, the **4PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs show poor performance with only 0.40% efficiency, possibly due to a cluster of aggregate formation, and pinholes in the microstructure, and low charge transporting ability. The performance of PSCs with **3PyPTPDAn** is on par with the Spiro-OMeTAD-based PSCs with 18.17% (Figure S16), which endorse the prospect of **3PyPTPDAn** as a suitable alternative to commercial Spiro-OMeTAD.

Figure 5. (a) Energy level diagram for Py-based HSLs along with perovskite and gold electrode, (b) cross-sectional SEM images of PSCs with **3PyPTPDAn**, the layers are differentiated by colors, (c) J - V curves of the with Py-based HSLs measured under simulated AM 1.5G illumination for the PSCs with reverse scans, (d) EQE curves of the corresponding PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn**, (e) corresponding integrated current (J_{int}) with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn**, (f) stabilized power output of PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn**. The statistical PV parameters: (g) V_{oc} , (h) J_{sc} , (i) FF , and (j) PCE with **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn**.

We can deduce (Figure 5d & 5e), the PSCs with **3PyPTPDAn** displayed a slightly higher EQE value at the entire wavelength than that of **2PyPTPDAn**, and thus yielded increased integrated current density (J_{int}) with 22.60 mA cm^{-2} compared with the 22.30 mA cm^{-2} for the

2PyPTPDAn. The hysteresis behavior was analyzed for PSCs fabricated with developed HSLs by calculating the hysteresis index (*HI*) (Figure S17 and Table S2). Following the equation: $HI = [J_{RS}(0.8V_{oc}) - J_{FS}(0.8V_{oc})]/J_{RS}(0.8V_{oc})$, where $J_{RS}(0.8V_{oc})$ and $J_{FS}(0.8V_{oc})$ denote the current density of J - V curves obtained by RS and FS at 80% of V_{oc} , respectively. The *HI* for PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn** is 0.203 and 0.079, respectively. The **3PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs showed reduction in hysteresis in comparison with the **2PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs, which can be attributed to higher charge-transporting abilities and uniform high-quality film and intimate interfacial contact.

The maximum power point trackers recorded the peak output power of the PSCs (Figure 5f). The stabilized current density and PCE values of **2PyPTPDAn**- and **3PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs were obtained as 18.49 mA cm⁻²/14.79% and 20.86 mA cm⁻²/17.52%, respectively, which is following the average PV results. The reproducibility of the PSCs with developed HSLs was analyzed and the statistical PV parameters are presented in Figure 5g–5j. The V_{oc} and FF with 1047.0 mV and 72.0% for the **3PyPTPDAn**-based PSC are higher than that **2PyPTPDAn** with 1041.7 mV and 66.0%, and this led to improved PCE.

We performed steady-state photoluminescence (PL) measurement to quantify, the hole extraction ability of HSLs, for this HSLs were deposited on perovskites coated quartz substrate. The pristine perovskite exhibited a strong PL emission peak at 801 nm, (**Figure 6a**), and the PL curve display quenching in the presence of **2Py**- and **3Py**- based HSL comparatively to **4PyPTPDAn**, signaling holes were efficiently extracted into the HSL, which is following the device performance. We noted a blue shift with the presence of HSL as compared to pristine perovskite, this could be ascribed to the filling of the shallow traps on the surface of perovskite.^{5,6}

To quantify the PV performance of PSCs with 3-position substitution Py-based HSL, we performed electrical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), to unravel the charge transport kinetics, carrier recombination at the perovskite surface, and grain boundaries. The PSCs were measured under dark conditions and V_{app} with a range of 0.75 V – 1.05 V, with a step of 0.05 V. The prime Nyquist plots with the $V_{\text{app}} = 0.9$ V (Figure 6b) were fitted and modeled by an equivalent circuit ($R - R_{\text{rec}} // C$). The recombination resistance (R_{rec}) values of PSCs with different HSLs measured under different V_{app} were registered and plotted (Figure 6c). The R_{rec} value decreases sharply with the increment of V_{app} , because of the perpetual carrier concentration injection. The R_{rec} value for the **3PyPTPDAn**- is higher than **2PyPTDAn**-based PSCs at similar V_{app} , pointing that **3PyPTPDAn** minimizes the charge carrier recombination at the perovskite/HSL interface considerably. The series resistance (R_s) and shunt resistance (R_{sh}) were obtained by fitting the J - V curves in the R_s and categorized in Table 2. The **3PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs owned the lower R_s and larger R_{sh} than that of **2PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs with R_s and R_{sh} . The trend of R_{sh} is following the R_{rec} and indicated that **3PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs have higher FF due to low series resistance and high hole carrier mobility.

Table 2 the PV parameters of the PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** HSLs.

HSL	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	R_s^a (Ω)	R_{sh}^b (k Ω)	HI^c
2PyPTPDAn	1041.7 1039.6 \pm 9.5	23.36 22.08 \pm 1.14	66.0 62.3 \pm 5.7	16.05 14.36 \pm 1.36	73	18.9	0.203
3PyPTPDAn	1047.0 1047.9 \pm 18.6	23.79 22.64 \pm 0.77	72.0 68.5 \pm 2.8	17.93 16.26 \pm 0.91	61	34.8	0.079
4PyPTPDAn	966.6 957.5 \pm 12.3	3.18 1.97 \pm 0.62	12.9 12.5 \pm 0.4	0.40 0.24 \pm 0.08	16279	1.3	–

^a R_s is the series resistance, ^b R_{sh} presents the shunt resistance. R_s and R_{sh} obtained from the champion device measured under reverse scan, the bold numbers showed the champion devices, ^c HI is hysteresis index ($HI = [J_{RS}(0.8V_{oc}) - J_{FS}(0.8V_{oc})]/J_{RS}(0.8V_{oc})$)

We further analyzed the charge lifetime (τ) of the PSCs based on different HSLs, obtained by following the equation: $\tau = 1/(2\pi f_p)$, where f_p is the frequency of the peak. It can be considered the electrochemical reaction of the charge transfer process at the perovskite/HSL interface.⁴⁶ The bode plots for the PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn** under $V_{app} = 0.95$ V and corresponding τ derived from devices under V_{app} ranging from 600 – 1000 mV are shown (Figure S18 and 6d). The τ values from **3PyPTPDAn** are still larger than that of the **2PyPTPDAn**-based PSC under the same V_{app} , implying a better charge transfer rate for **3PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs.

Figure 6 (a) The steady-state photoluminescence of pristine perovskite and perovskite with 2Py-, 3Py-, 4Py-based HSLs. (b) Nyquist plots with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn** based PSCs under $V_{app}=0.95$ V, (c) recombination resistance (R_{rec}) was extracted from Nyquist plots of PSCs with

2PyPTPDAn and **3PyPTPDAn** under different V_{app} in dark conditions, (d) electron lifetime for PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn** under different applied voltage, (e) C - V characteristics with PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn**, and (f) J - V curves for the PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn** measured under dark conditions.

The capacitance–voltage (C - V) measurement was conducted to scrutinize the internal electrical process affected by the pyridine isomer in PSCs. The charge accumulation at the electrode interface can be characterized by the amount of capacitance, which showed a linear correlation with the charge accumulation.⁴⁷ Importantly, the undesirable charge accumulation is ascribed to hysteresis phenomena.^{48,49} The capacitance value of the PSCs with **3PyPTPDAn** is smaller than that with **2PyPTPDAn** at V_{app} altering from -1.5 V – 1.25 V (Figure 6e), revealing less charge accumulation at the interface in the PSCs with **3PyPTPDAn** and showed low hysteresis behavior in the **3PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs as compared with **2PyPTPDAn**.⁵⁰

The J - V curves characteristics under dark conditions of the PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn** are measured and the semi-logarithmic J - V plots are shown (Figure 6f). The reverse saturation current density (J_0) and n can be evaluated by fitting the exponential region of the semi-logarithmic curve with the Shockley ideal diode equation.^{51,52} The ideality factor of the real diode (n) and the reverse saturation current density (J_0) are listed in Table S3. The values of the [n , J_0] were [3.04, 9.9×10^{-5} mA cm⁻²] and [2.63, 3.5×10^{-5} mA cm⁻²] for the PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn**, respectively. The lower values of the n and J_0 for **3PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs indicate the controlled interfacial recombination and effective charge extraction and transport, to allow optimized PV performance.⁵³

In addition to the PV performance, device stability under various stress conditions was investigated by tracking performance drop as a function of time. Firstly, the performance of unencapsulated PSCs under ambient conditions (30%–70% relative humidity (RH) and room temperature) is recorded (Figure 7a). The 2Py and 3Py-based PSCs hold 78.6% and 86.3% of their initial value, respectively, after aging for over 1,300 h, while the control device with Spiro-OMeTAD reduced to 72.7%. Secondly, the maximum power point tracking for the unsealed PSCs exposed to moisture and continuous 1 sun illumination simulated by white LED were recorded (Figure 7b). The device with **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn** sustained 71.8% and 51.5% of their initial efficiency, respectively, whereas, the control PSC drops to 44.9% in around 100 min. These results suggested that Py-based HSLs, especially **3PyPTPDAn**, are an attractive candidate to improve stability under stress (only moisture) and multi-stress (moisture and light) conditions. The water contact angle of perovskite with different HSLs was measured (Figure 7c), **3PyPTPDAn** showed a higher value than that of **2PyPTPDAn** and Spiro-OMeTAD. This remains constant during the measurement conditions (24 s). The hydrophobic properties of perovskite/**3PyPTPDAn** can prevent water penetration into the perovskite layer, thus endowing moisture stability.

Figure 7 (a) Normalized PCE plots of PSCs with **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and Spiro-OMeTAD aged under ambient conditions (30-70% RH) for around 1,300 h, (b) maximum power point tracking under humidity and 1-sun illumination of the unencapsulated device with **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and Spiro-OMeTAD, (c) contact angles variation of the perovskite layers with doped **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn**, and Spiro-OMeTAD with time, inset: photos of contact angle after dropping water, 24 s for (i) **2PyPTPDAn** / (ii) **3PyPTPDAn**, and 20 s for (iii) Spiro-OMeTAD, respectively.

The PSC with Py-based HSLs, especially **3PyPTPDAn** gave on par PV performance but with improved environmental stability. To validate its commercial prospects, we made a cost analysis following published procedures at the laboratory stage (Table S4 – S11), the calculated costs of **2PyPTPDAn** and **3PyPTPDAn** are c.a. ~ 35.1 € and ~ 39.0 € per gram, respectively. The calculated cost of these pyridine-based HSLs is significantly lower than the commercial Spiro-OMeTAD (c.a. 300 € per gram) and has a higher yield (62% for **2PyPTPDAn** and 56% for **3PyPTPDAn**) than Spiro-OMeTAD (45%). Additionally, the cost per milliliter of HSLs with **3PyPTPDAn** (**2PyPTPDAn**) is 1.8 € per mL remarkably lower than that of Spiro-OMeTAD (28.9 € per mL). This cost analysis recommends **3PyPTPDAn** can be viable as an alternative HSL for perovskite-based devices and would accelerate the exploitation.

3. Conclusion

We have designed and investigated three pyridine isomer-based small molecules as p-type semiconductors. We probed the impact of pyridine isomers on the microstructure and electro-optical properties through an array of techniques and noted that isomer position has a bearing on

the electro-optical properties. Electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy presents similar g_{iso} values, however, the hyperfine coupling constant (a^N) is lower for **4Py** than for **2Py** and **3PyPTPDAn** and the signal intensity was an order of magnitude lower for **4Py**. The hyperfine coupling constant suggests an improved electron density for **3PyPTPDAn**. The perovskite solar cells fabricated with **3PyPTPDAn** yielded a higher performance than that of **2PyPTPDAn** and **4PyPTPDAn**, which was on par with Spiro-OMeTAD, but the **3Py** presented improved stability under moisture and light condition. **3PyPTPDAn** is empowered with unparalleled optoelectrical properties and film-forming ability compared to **2PyPTPDAn** and **4PyPTPDAn** while being cost-competitive to enabling the transfer of laboratory results to industrial manufacturing.

4. Experimental Section

4.1 Synthetic of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** HSLs

The synthesis scheme for the novel HSLs and the synthetic route to intermediate including **1a**, **1b**, **1c**, and **PTPDAn** were shown in SI.

Synthesis of x PyPTPDAn ($x=2, 3$ and 4) To a 50 mL round bottom flask x -bromopyridine ($x=2, 3$ and 4) (100 mg, 0.637 mmol), 4,4'-(10H-phenothiazine-3,7-diyl)bis(N,N-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline) (PTPDAn) (512 mg, 0.637 mmol), sodium tert-butoxide (122.3 mg, 1.274 mmol), and dry toluene (20 mL) were added. The mixture was purged with N_2 for 10 min and $P(tBu)_3HBF_4$ (9.23 mg, 0.05 mmol) and $Pd(OAc)_2$ (5.72 mg, 0.04 mmol) were added. The reaction mixture was refluxed under N_2 for 24 h. After completion of the reaction, monitored with TLC, the reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and the solution was filtered to remove insoluble solids. The filtrate was concentrated in a vacuum and purified by column chromatography (silica gel, hexane: ethyl acetate 8:4 (v/v) as eluent) to give X PyPTPDAn ($X=2,$

3, and 4) as a solid. The final product of **2PyPTPDAn**, **3PyPTPDAn**, and **4PyPTPDAn** are shown white, and light yellow, with the corresponding yield of 62%, 56%, and 50%, respectively. All of the analytical data ($^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}$ NMR spectroscopy and mass spectra are shown in SI).

4.2 Device fabrication

The FTO substrates (NSG10) were first cleaned by 2% Hellmanex solution, acetone, and isopropanol with an ultrasonicator. The substrates treated with UV-ozone were heated to 500 °C for over 30 min. The blocking TiO_2 layer was sprayed with the precursor solution [1 mL titanium (IV) diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) ethanol solution and 19 mL ethanol] and kept heating for 30 min after spray deposition. The mesoporous TiO_2 film was spin-coated at 4,000 rpm for 30 s using the 30NRD solution in ethanol with 0.13 g/mL. The as-prepared TiO_2 were post-heating at 125°C for 15 min and 500 °C for 30 min. The perovskite films were prepared by dynamics two-step methods, reported by our group.⁵ In short, the 1.3M PbI_2 in a mixed solvent (volume ratio of DMF/DMSO:9/1) were heated at 70 °C for 4 h and the mixed organic cation with FAI/MABr/MACl (60/6/6 mg/mL) in isopropanol were dissolved at room temperature. The PbI_2 solution heated at 70 °C was spin-coated atop *b&mp*- TiO_2 with 2,000 rpm for 30 s and kept under vacuum for 1 min. The 100 μL organic cation was dropped to the PbI_2 film, awaiting 5 s, and spin-coated with 2,000 rpm for 30 s. The as-prepared perovskite films were annealed at 150 °C for 15 min in the glovebox. The 50 mM novel pyridine-based HTM solution was dissolved in chlorobenzene with common dopants (LiTFSI and *t*-BP with the mole ratio of 0.5 and 3.3, respectively). The Spiro-OMeTAD was prepared by dissolving 72.3 mg/mL in chlorobenzene with 17.5 μL LiTFSI solution (520 mg/mL in acetonitrile) and 28.8 μL *t*-BP. Finally, the gold electrode with 70 nm was thermally deposited.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Supporting Information

Synthesis for the intermediate materials, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR, and HRMS spectra of all the new compounds, cost calculations.

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